

Assessment of Arable Land Loss Due to Urbanization Using Remote Sensing and Gis: A Study of Jos South Local Government Area of Plateau State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Urbanization is threatening the limited arable land in Nigeria, this study assessed the arable (cultivated) land loss due to urban growth in Jos South Local Government Area from 1993-2013. The study utilized data from field surveys, remote sensed data and geographical information system technique, four main methods of data analysis were adopted in this study namely calculation of the Area in hectares of the resulting land use/land cover types for each study year and subsequently comparing the results, Markov Chain and Cellular Automata Analysis for predicting change, Overlay Operations and Maximum Likelihood Classification. The results of the study show that built up areas in 1993 occupied the least among the total land area with about 9.45% coverage representing 4833.6 hectares, Jos South Local Government Area recorded increase in spatial growth between 1993 to 2013 as built up area increased in 2013 with 18.74% coverage representing about 9589.29 hectares with a difference of 4755.69 hectares. The pattern of growth in between 2003 and 2013 recorded an exponential increase compared to that of 1993 to 2003, as it recorded about 6.74% a difference of 3456.78 hectares from that of 1993 to 2003 that recorded about 2.53% a difference of 1298.88 hectares. Arable lands are gradually on the decline as both vegetation and rock outcrop have given way to built-up areas. From the projection made on land use coverage in the study to the year 2023 it is obvious that there will reduction in arable lands. Jos South local Government Area is largely a producer of tuber, vegetables and grains and the alarming rate of development mostly attributed to rapid population increase, migration and improvements in the standard of living of the people due to commerce, its status as a local council headquarters are the major determinants of loss in arable lands which in the nearest future will sharply reduce the agricultural output of Jos South Local Government Area, It can be concluded that the urbanization is one of the dominant degradation process in Jos South Local Government Area. Recommendations were put forward by the study to reduce the loss of arable land to other landuses due to urbanization in the study area

Keywords: Arable land, Urban growth, Remote Sensing, Geographic Information System (GIS),

INTRODUCTION

Urban growth is one of the foremost threat facing arable lands in Nigeria. Also urban growth is one of the prominent features of industrial era and is also a major driving force altering local and regional environments. The simultaneous growth in both population and economic output per capital and the consequent changes in land use pattern impose a cost to the natural environment. (Cohen, 2004; Tang *et al.*, 2005; Ifatimehin and Ufuah; 2006. Ifatimehin and Musa, 2008).

Rapid urban growth and increasing land use changes due to population and economic growth is being witnessed in cities all over the world. The cities expanding in all directions resulting in large-scale urban sprawl and changes in urban land use (Manish *et al.*, 2012). The increase in economic development and urbanization of Jos City has resulted in the significant loss of Arable land where Jos-South L.G.A. is also part of the city of Jos. It is understood that; this will cause severe environmental consequences in a long-term. So it is important to evaluate the magnitude, pattern and types of arable loss for managing future arable protection and development.

The impending ecological and environmental threats resulting from rapid urbanization comprises of climate change, ozone depletion, alterations in biogeochemical cycles, widespread dispersal and disposal of non-biodegradable solid wastes and persistent liquid, gas, chemical and other pollutants, deforestation, increase in the volume, rate of surface run-off, a decrease in ground water recharge and base flow, flooding, altering of natural hydrological condition within a watershed and modifying water balance (Fohrer *et al.*, 2001; Rosal *et al.*, 2004).

Kombe and Kreibich (2000) perceived that rapid urban growth would initiate improvement of both living conditions and quality of environment, but it is understood that the conversion of Arable, vegetation and wetlands to urban areas and the un-attending population growth usually come with a vast increase in impervious surfaces, consumption and utilization of goods and building on natural drainages. (USEPA 2001, Ifetimehin, 2007).

Satellite remote sensing had been widely applied and taken as a useful and effective tool in detecting land use change (including farmland loss) (Weng, 2001). The common method is the post-classification which is to compare two or more data of remote sensing images which can cover the same study area. Also, image differencing, vegetation index differencing, principal components analysis, direct multi-data classification, univariate image differencing, Image regression, image rationing, change vector analysis are used in a lot of land use and land cover researches including farmland loss (Mas, 1999).

The primary objective of this study therefore is to provide arable loss data (1993 – 2013) of Jos – South L.G.A by the method of post classification using Landsat TM/ETM+ images, and seeks to predict expected changes in the next 10 years, while the specific objectives are to: map out the various landuse in the study area for three different years (1993, 2003 and 2013), identify the spatial relationship between urban growth and Arable lands in the study area, identify the rate and magnitude of Arable land loss in the study area, predict the trend of Arable land loss by 2023.

The Study Area

Jos south local government area is located between latitudes 9° 30' to 10° N and longitude 8° 30' E. It is situated at the north western part of the state with its headquarters at Bukuru, which is about 15 km from the state capital, Jos. The local government area has four districts: Du, Gyel, Kuru and Vwang districts. The local government area has total land area of about 1,037 km² with a population of 306,716 (NPC, 2006). It has a cool climatic condition due to its altitude. The coldest period is between November and February with an average mean daily temperature of 18°C, while it gets warm between March and April before the onset of rain. The rainy season, which is between the months of May and October, has its peak in August. The mean annual rainfall varies between 1347.5 and 1460 mm per annum (Michael, 2012). The people of Jos south were predominantly farmers and hunters, Common food crops grown in the area include Irish potato, sweet-potato, maize, millet, Acha, tomato and many other varieties of vegetables. Due to the ever green vegetation and tse-tse-free nature of the area, cattle rearing and grazing has been quite profitable and poultry farming is a viable business in the area. The conducive environment for cattle rearing has attracted investors such as the Integrated Dairy farm, Vom (formerly WAMCO) which produces dairy products, as well as ECWA Rural Development Company Limited which also deals in poultry production and other veterinary services (Gwom, 1992).

Table1: Population Growth of Jos-South

Year	Population	Increase	Growth Rate
1991	237,408	-	-
2006	306,716	69,308	29.19%

Source: National population Commission, 2006

Fig. 1. Map of Study Area

(source: Author's Lab work 2014)

Materials and Method

In the course of this study, software and hardware were the main materials used. As for the software, **ArcGIS 9.3 version** was employed for the delineation of the study area from the map, clipping of the Image to the study area and preparation of the image for analysis. **Google Earth Pro** is internet based software employed to download an internet image representing the study area which served as a referenced image and a complementary to reconnaissance survey. **IDRISI Taiga** is GIS software that was employed in this study to do all the necessary analysis on the image leading to the final results. While on the other hand, the hardware include: **Computer** being the main laboratory equipment used in this study where all the laboratory work were done in it. For the purpose of reconnaissance survey, **Global positioning system (GPS)** was used to identify various locations within the study area as (Appendix A1). Land cover data was extracted from the United States Geological Service (USGS) web site (<http://www.usgs.gov>). This land cover raster coverage was originally built from 30 meter Landsat 5 Thermal Mapping (TM) data from the early 1990, Landsat 30m ETM for the year 2003 and 2013 Landsat 8 OLI image. Google earth image covering the study area was also downloaded free from Google image website using Google Earth software, which will be used as a reference image and will complement the groundthruing exercise. The study area is a local government area, therefore a digital local government boundary map and Nigerian Administrative map was also obtained from National Center for Remote Sensing (NCRS) Jos for mapping out the study area from the satellite image. Based on the prior knowledge of the study area for many years, and a brief reconnaissance survey with additional information from previous research in the study area, a classification scheme was developed for the study area after Anderson et al (1971). The classification scheme developed gives a rather broad classification where the land use land cover was identified by a single digit. Additional spatial data were collected with a handheld GPS

(Global Positioning System) during reconnaissance survey (Appendix A1). Locations of settlements, watering points, and cultivated areas were recorded. The GPS had an accuracy of plus or minus 5 meters, so for consistency, the reading at each point was taken at or close to the front of the intended land use type, the purpose was to confirm what was seen on ground to what was on the image. This was done whenever the GPS fully acquired connection from the satellite at the selected point. The recorded points were used during training site creation and also reserve for accuracy assessment. The Landsat satellite imageries of 1993, 2003 and 2013 downloaded from United States Geological Service (USGS) web site (<http://www.usgs.gov>), using the path and Row 188/053 of the area of interest on the map search interface. Geo-referencing and coordinate system creation was not necessary at this point as it was already pre-geo-referenced and ortho-rectified from the source using Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) as its projection and WGS84 as its ellipsoid. The downloaded Google earth image of the area was geo-referenced and digitized. The digital map of the local government was digitized and used as a frame to subset the Google image and individual band of Landsat images which were individually exported and staked into IDRISI Tiger environment one at a time. The study area was sub-mapped and enhanced using the contrast stretching techniques of the global contrast enhancement method, the spectral band were combined to obtain a colour composite by formation of bands 4, 3 and 2 for both 1986 and 1999 respectively, the result of the colour composite is shown below in figure 2, 3 and 3 respectively.

Image classification is a conventional change detection method which provides an avenue to create series of Land cover maps, and in order to produce land use land cover maps after classification that will the various changes that occur due to loss of Arable in the study area., the satellite imageries of Landsat TM of 1986 and Landsat ETM of 1999 was classified using maximum likelihood classification algorithm. The images were imported into IDRISI Taiga for classification that is the process of extraction of differentiated classes or theme from raw remotely sensed digital satellite data (Meyer, 1995). Each cluster of observations is a class. A class occupies its own area in the feature space i.e. a specific part of the feature space corresponds to a specific class. Once the classes have been defined in the feature space, each image pixel observation can be compared to these classes and assigned to the corresponding class. Classes to be distinguished in an image classification need to have different spectral characteristics, which can be analyzed by comparing spectra reflectance curve.

Methods of Data Analysis

Four main methods of data analysis were adopted in this study.

- (i) Calculation of the Area in hectares of the resulting land use/land cover types for each study year and subsequently comparing the results.
- (ii) Markov Chain and Cellular Automata Analysis for predicting change
- (iii) Overlay Operations
- (iv) Maximum Likelihood Classification

The first three methods above were used for identifying change in the land use types. Therefore, they have been combined in this study.

The comparison of the land use land cover statistics assisted in identifying the percentage change, trend and rate of change between 1993 and 2013. In achieving this, the first task was to develop a table showing the area in hectares and the percentage change for each year (1993, 2003 and 2013) measured against each land use land cover type. Percentage change to determine the trend of change can then be calculated by dividing observed change by sum of changes multiplied by 100

$$(Trend)Percentage\ Change = \frac{Observed\ Change}{Sum\ of\ Change} * 100$$

In obtaining annual rate of change, the percentage change is divided by 100 and multiplied by the number of study year 1993 – 2003 (10years) 2003 – 2013 (10years). Markov Chain Analysis and Cellular Automata Analysis were used in modeling land use change and addition of spatial character to the changes. Overlay operations which is the last method of the three, identifies the actual location and magnitude of change although this was limited to the built-up land. Boolean logic was applied to the result through the reclass module of idrisi32 which assisted in mapping out separately areas of change for which magnitude was later calculated for.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results are presented inform of maps, charts and statistical tables. They include the static, change and projected land use land cover of each class.

Land Use Land Cover Distribution

The static land use land cover distribution for each study year as derived from the maps are presented in the table below

Table 2. Land Use Land Cover Distribution (1991, 2003, 2013)

LANDUSE/LAND COVER CATEGORIES	1993		2003		2013	
	AREA(Ha.)	AREA (%)	AREA (Ha.)	AREA (%)	AREA (Ha.)	AREA (%)
BARE LAND	32211.45	62.95	28124.46	54.96	24571.63	48.02
BUILT-UP AREA	4833.63	9.45	6132.51	11.98	9589.29	18.74
ARABLE LAND	10054.62	19.65	13449.33	26.28	11820.22	23.10
WATER BODY	967.93	1.89	1436.65	2.8	12084.95	4.07
VEGETATION	3104.37	6.07	2029.05	3.97	3105.91	6.07
TOTAL	51,172.00	100	51,172.00	100	51,172.00	100

(Source: Authors Field work, 2014)

The values presented in table 2 above represents the static area of each land use land cover category for each study year. Water body in 1991 occupies the least class with just 1.89% of the total classes. The local government occupied the largest land mass among the three local government that formed the Jos metropolis and farming id the major occupation among the indigenes. That's why there is more open land of 62.95% and arable land of 19.65% in 1991. Because of abundant land mass built-up increases through 2003 and 2013

respectively. New estates are coming up leading to the encroachment of arable land that are close to the town that reduces their size in 2003 and 2013 respectively.

Fig.2: Classified image of 1991 Fig.3 Classified image of 2003 Fig.4 Classified image of 2013

LANDUSE/LAND COVER CATEGORIES	1991 – 2003		2003 – 2013		ANNUAL RATE OF CHANGE	
	AREA (Ha.)	%CHANGE	AREA (Ha.)	%CHANGE	91 – 03	03 - 13
BARE LAND	-4086.99	-13	-3552.83	-13	-1.08	-1.3
BUILT- UP AREA	1298.88	27	3456.79	56	2.25	5.6
ARABLE LAND	3394.71	34	-1629.11	-12	2.83	-1.2
WATERBODY	468.72	48	648.30	45	4	4.5
VEGETATION	-1075.32	-35	-1076.86	53	-2.91	5.3

Table 3 Land use land cover change of Jos-South: 1991, 2003 and 2013

(Source: Authors Field work, 2014)

Transition Probability Matrix

The transition probability matrix records the probability that each land cover category will change to the other category. This matrix is produced by the multiplication of each column in the transition probability matrix by the number of cells of corresponding land use in the later image.

For the 5 by 5 matrix table 4 presented, the rows represent the older land cover categories and the column represents the newer categories. Although this matrix can be used as a direct input for specification of the prior probabilities in maximum likelihood classification of the remotely sensed imagery, it was however used in predicting land use land cover of 2023.

Table 4: Transitional Probability table derived from the land use land cover map of 1986 and 2001

CLASSES	Bare Land	Built-up Area	Arable Land	Water body	Vegetation
Bare Land	0.3519	0.2777	0.0197	0.0388	0.1119
Built-up Area	0.0310	0.3054	0.0426	0.0210	0.0000
Arable Land	0.0494	0.3728	0.2003	0.0286	0.1489
Water body	0.2718	0.0595	0.0308	0.2518	0.2860
Vegetation	0.1239	0.2037	0.0248	0.0346	0.3130

Row categories represent land use land cover classes in 2013, whilst column categories represent 2023 classes. As seen from the table, bare land has a 0.3519 will remain. Also built-up having the highest with 0.3054 will not change in 2023. Arable land with 0.2003 has a probability of changing to built-up. Vegetation during this period will likely reduce its position to built-up. Water body which has a 0.2518 probability of changing to bare land; which may not however be a true projection of this class except there is an occurrence of drought in the region.

Land Use Land Cover Projection for 2023

Table 5: Projected Land use land cover for 2023

LAND USE LAND COVER CLASSES		Bare Land	Built-up Area	Arable Land	Water Body	Vegetation
2023	AREA IN					
	HECTARES	22,381.58	13,161.03	8321.13	2175.67	5132.59
	AREA IN					
	PERCENTAGE	43.77	25.72	16.2	64.21	10.03

Fig.5 Predicted image of 2023

Table 5 shows the statistic of land use land cover projection for 2023. Comparing the percentage representations of this table and that of table 2, there exist similarities in the observed distribution particularly in 2013. This may tend to suggest no change in the classes between 2013 and 2023, but a careful look at the area in hectares between these two tables shows a change though meager. Thus in table 3, bare land still maintains the highest position in the class whilst water body retains its least position. vegetation takes up the next position, followed by arable land and finally, built-up area.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates the ability of GIS and Remote Sensing in capturing spatial-temporal data. Attempt was made to capture as accurate as possible five land use land cover classes as they change through time. Except for the inability to accurately map out some area of the water body in 2003 but the size was complemented when compared with the total land mass.

The five classes were distinctly produced for each study year but with more emphasis on built-up land as it is a combination of anthropogenic activities that make up this class; and indeed, it is one that affects the other classes. However, the result of the work shows a rapid growth in built-up land between 2003 and 2013 this may be attributed to relocation of many people from the city centre to a new layout around the local government.. It was also observed that change by 2023 may likely follow the trend in 2003/2013 all things being equal.

In conclusion, Jos south local government is experiencing a fast developmental growth where government allocated land for building at the detriment of farm land which need to be looked in to. With the changes shown on the map, if precautionary measures were not taken land for agricultural purposes will start to have a set back and may affect the agricultural activities of the area.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were given as: all land meant for building must be registered with government before building commence, fertile areas must be protected against any development, at a particular interval government should take into cognizance of Land use and Land cover to ascertain changes that are taking place.

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APPENDIX A1: GPS points at the study area

S/N	LOCATION	LATITUDE (N)	LONGITUDE (E)	ELEVATION
1	Zarmaganda	09° 49. 362 ¹	08° 51.957 ¹	1241m
2	Before bukuru junction (bridge)	09° 48. 888 ¹	08° 52.084 ¹	1234m
3	Bukuru L.G.A secretarial	09° 47. 951 ¹	08° 51.698 ¹	1247m
4	Gyal 'A' gero road	09° 48. 129 ¹	08° 51.101 ¹	1222m
5	Bukuru town (market)	09° 37. 331 ¹	08° 51.991 ¹	1277m
6	Police staff college	09° 45. 508 ¹	08° 51.627 ¹	1258m
7	Mararrabanjama'a	09° 43. 200 ¹	08° 51.948 ¹	1264m
8	Sabonlayi road (kuru). New road	09° 42. 644 ¹	08° 50.334 ¹	1308m
9	Government science school kuru	09° 42. 040 ¹	08° 50.189 ¹	1319m
10	Zawan	09° 44. 722 ¹	08° 52.596 ¹	1275m
11	Du (zawan road to Du)	09° 45. 518 ¹	08° 53.143 ¹	1299m
12	Loti (Du)	09° 45. 423 ¹	08° 52.748 ¹	1272m
13	Rabin (Du)	09° 45.716 ¹	08° 53.349 ¹	1295m
14	Shen road (Du)	09° 46.608 ¹	08° 53.648 ¹	1295m
15	Shen village	09° 46.310 ¹	08° 54.615 ¹	1317m
16	Dwei Du	09° 48.732 ¹	08° 55.246 ¹	1322m
17	Dura	09° 49.939 ¹	08° 55.257 ¹	1312m
18	Rayfield	09° 50.247 ¹	08° 54.960 ¹	1300m
19	Kwang	09° 50.817 ¹	08° 55.758 ¹	1318m
20	Lamingoraod	09° 53.980 ¹	08° 56.096 ¹	129m